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Review Article

**A REVIEW ON RISK MANAGEMENT OF PHARMACEUTICAL
PRODUCT AND PHARMACEUTICAL TOXICOLOGY**Lavanya J M^{*1}, Shibina S², Aparna P³, Prasobh G.R⁴

^{1*} Student, seventh semester B Pharm, Sree Krishna College of pharmacy and Research Centre, Parassala, Thiruvanthapuram, Kerala, India -695502., ² Student, seventh semester B Pharm, Sree Krishna College of pharmacy and Research Centre, Parassala, Thiruvanthapuram, Kerala, India-695502., ³ Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Sree Krishna College of pharmacy and Research Centre, Parassala, Thiruvanthapuram, Kerala, India-695502., ⁴ Principal, Sree Krishna College of pharmacy and Research Centre, Parassala, Thiruvanthapuram, Kerala, India-695502.

Article Received: June 2024**Accepted: June 2024****Published: July 2024****Abstract:**

Risk management in the pharmaceutical industry is a critical process that ensures the safety, efficacy, and quality of pharmaceutical products. This discipline involves identifying, assessing, and mitigating risks throughout the lifecycle of a drug, from development to post-market surveillance. Key strategies include rigorous clinical testing, thorough regulatory compliance, and continuous monitoring of adverse events. Pharmaceutical toxicology, a vital component of risk management, focuses on the study of adverse effects of chemical substances on living organisms. It provides essential data that help predict potential toxicities and guide the safe development of new drugs. Toxicological assessments are performed through various in vitro and in vivo studies, providing insights into the mechanisms of toxicity, dose-response relationships, and potential human health impacts. Effective integration of risk management and toxicological evaluation is crucial for minimizing risks and ensuring patient safety.

Keywords: *Mitigating, Toxicological, dose-response relationships, clinical testing, Regulatory compliance.*

Corresponding author:

Lavanya J M,
Seventh semester B Pharm,
Sree Krishna College of pharmacy and Research Centre,
Parassala, Thiruvanthapuram, Kerala, India -695502
Ph.No:0471-2224747
E-mail: lavanya.johnson.mary.89@gmail.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Pharmaceutical risk management and toxicology are crucial for ensuring the safety and efficacy of medications. They involve identifying, assessing, and mitigating potential risks, including adverse effects and drug interactions. Pharmaceutical toxicology involves rigorous processes, including testing, adherence to regulations, and ongoing monitoring, promoting public health and confidence in pharmaceutical products. Quality Risk Management (QRM) is a systematic process that minimizes risks to product quality throughout its life-cycle, optimizing benefits and balancing risks. It involves evaluation, control, communication, and review of risks to the quality of medicinal products. QRM is a mandatory regulatory requirement for healthcare organizations, supporting science-based and practical decisions in quality systems such as Validation, Quality Defects Investigation, Auditing, Inspection, Documentation, and Training.[1]

Principles of Quality Risk Management

The four primary principles of Quality Risk Management (QRM) for pharmaceutical products include assessing risk based on scientific knowledge, being dynamic, iterative, responsive to change, ensuring effort and documentation are proportional to risk, and embedding continuous development.[2]

Initiating a Quality Risk Management Process

Steps used to initiate and plan a quality risk management process might include the following

Risk Assessment-Risk assessment consists of the identification of hazards and the analysis and evaluation of risks associated with exposure to those hazards. It includes risk identification, risk analysis and risk evaluation. Three fundamental questions are often helpful.

1. What might go wrong?
2. What is the possibility that it will go wrong?
3. What are the consequences?

Risk identification is an organized use of information to identify hazards referring to the risk. Information can include historical data, theoretical analysis, and the concerns of stakeholders. Risk identification addresses the "What might go wrong?" question, including identifying the possible consequences.

Risk analysis is the estimation of the risk associated with the identified hazards. It is the qualitative or quantitative process of linking the likelihood of occurrence and severity of harms. In some risk management tools, the ability to detect the harm (detectability) also factors in the estimation of risk. [3]

Risk evaluation compares the identified and analyzed risk against given risk criteria. Different Steps Involved in the Risk Assessment are: Collect & organize the information, Formulate the Risk Question, Choose Tool, Identify Risks Factors and Related Hazards, Define the Risk Components & Scales, Evaluate the risk for each hazard, Determine acceptability of risks, Determine Action Threshold, Apply the tool. [4]

Risk Control-Risk control includes decision making to reduce and/or accept risks. The intention of risk control is to reduce the risk to an acceptable level. The amount of effort used for risk control should be proportional to the significance of the risk.

Risk reduction focuses on processes for mitigation or avoidance of quality risk when it exceeds a specified level. Risk reduction might include actions taken to mitigate the severity and probability of harm.

Risk acceptance is a decision to accept risk. For some types of harms, even the best quality risk management practices might not entirely eliminate risk. In these circumstances, it might be agreed that an appropriate quality risk management strategy has been applied and that quality risk is reduced to a specified (acceptable) level.

Risk Review is the output/results of the risk management process should be reviewed to take into account new knowledge and experience. Once a quality risk management process has been initiated, that process should continue to be utilized for events that might impact the original quality risk management decision.

Risk Communication is the sharing of information about risk and risk management between the decision makers and others. The output/result of the quality risk management process should be appropriately communicated and documented. [5]

Pharmaceutical toxicology:

It involves a series of tests and evaluations to assess the safety of a drug. These tests are conducted in vitro (in the laboratory) and in vivo (in living organisms). In vitro tests are conducted on isolated cells or tissues to determine the potential toxicity of a drug. In vivo tests are conducted on animals to assess the safety of a drug before it is tested on humans. The first step in pharmaceutical toxicology is to determine the toxic dose of a drug, which is the amount of the drug that causes toxicity in test subjects. This is determined by administering various doses of the drug to test subjects and monitoring their responses. The results of these

tests are used to establish a safe dosage range for human use. [6]

Key areas in pharmaceutical toxicology:

1. Preclinical toxicology

Acute toxicity studies this is a short term assessment and evaluation of potential hazard test substance or consequences of single dose of a test substance. Acute toxicity testing may be used in risk assessments of chemicals for humans and non-target environmental organisms. Acute toxicity study is better described as LD50, which is defined as the dose which kills 50% of animals. LD50 is used for the estimation of the toxicity of the chemical agents.

Importance of acute toxicity testing involves to identify the target organ of toxicity, to provide safety measures and monitoring guidelines for workers involved in the development and testing and test substance, to provide information needed or the dose selection in prolonged toxicity studies, to generate data containing the adverse effects

Sub-acute toxicity studies this study is conducted to determine organs affected by different dose levels. This study access the nature of toxic dose under more realistic situation than the acute toxicity studies.

Chronic toxicity studies this study is basically to determine the organs affected and to check whether the drug is potentially carcinogenic or not. This test extends over a long period of time and it involves large groups of laboratory animals. Chronic toxicity is the development of adverse effects as the result of long term exposure to a toxicant or other stressor. It can manifest as direct lethality but more commonly refers to sub lethal endpoints such as decreased growth, reduced reproduction, or behavioral changes such as impacted swimming performance.

Genotoxicity, mutagenicity and teratogenicity: Genotoxicity covers a broader spectrum of endpoints than mutagenicity, includes DNA damage assessments. DNA damage are not themselves necessarily transmissible to the next generation of cells, pre-mutagenic. *Mutagenicity* refers to the production of transmissible genetic alterations. Somatic cell genotoxicity may lead to cancer. Germ cell genotoxicity may lead to infertility or diseased children.

Teratogenicity Capacity of a drug to cause fetal abnormalities when administered to the pregnant mother. Placenta does not consider a strict barrier and any drug can cross it to a greater or lesser extent. The

embryo is one of the most dynamic biological systems. [7]

2. Clinical toxicology

Human safety studies clinical trials are scientific investigations that examine and evaluate the safety and efficacy of new drugs, devices, tests, or lifestyle interventions using human subjects. A common approach by which to achieve this aim is through randomization, whereby patients are assigned to a treatment group by random selection. Patients and trial personnel are deliberately kept unaware of which patient is on the new drug. Clinical trials must be designed in an ethical manner so that patients are not denied the benefit of usual treatments. Patients must give their voluntary consent that they appreciate the purpose of the trial. [8]

PHASES:

For commercial purposes, trials have been classified into various phases, determined by the pharmaceutical industry based on the four phases of development of a particular drug:

Phase I - Test Drug in Healthy Volunteers

Test the effects of a new therapeutic agent in healthy volunteers following successful animal studies. These examine how the drug is handled in the human body (pharmacokinetics/pharmacodynamics), particularly with respect to immediate short-term safety of higher doses.

Phase II - Test drug in Patients with the Disease

Examine dose-response curves in patients using different dosages of the therapeutic agent in usually a small group of patients with a particular disease.

Phase III - Test Drug against Placebo

A new drug is tested in a controlled fashion in a large patient population against a placebo or standard therapy. This is a key phase, where a drug must establish superior or equivalent efficacy to standard therapy or placebo. A positive study in Phase III is often known as a landmark study.

Phase IV - Test Drug While in the Marketplace

A post marketing study as the drug has already been granted regulatory approval/license. These later studies are crucial for gathering additional safety information from a larger group of patients with respect to the long-term safety of the drug or for establishing a drug in a new or wider group of patients. [9]

Adverse drug reactions an adverse drug reaction (ADR) is any undesirable effect of a drug beyond

anticipated therapeutic effects occurring during clinical use.

Classification of Adverse Drug Reactions ADRs can be divided schematically into two major categories:

1. Type A reactions are common, predictable and may occur in any individual. These reactions are the most frequent and can be observed in as many as 25–45% of patients. These represent an exaggeration of the known primary and/or secondary pharmacological actions of the drug, they are dose related and could probably be avoided and/or foreseen.

2. Type B ADRs are uncommon and unpredictable and occur in susceptible individuals^[10]

3. Regulatory toxicology

•Compliance with Guidelines: Follow guidelines from regulatory bodies like the FDA and EMA

•Risk-Benefit Analysis: Weigh the therapeutic benefits against potential risks.^[11]

It consists of collecting, processing and evaluating incidents, distribution, and control of disease towards the protection of health against harmful toxicants. It supports the development of standard protocols and new testing methods. A number of international bodies and authorities promote the sound management of chemicals at national and international level, they are: ICH, WHO, FDA, OECD.^[12]

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, effective risk management of pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical toxicology are paramount for ensuring the safety and efficacy of medications. By implementing rigorous processes for identifying, assessing, and mitigating risks, pharmaceutical companies can minimize the likelihood of adverse effects and drug interactions. Pharmaceutical toxicology ensure that products meet stringent safety standards, providing assurance to healthcare professionals and patients alike. Continuous monitoring and adherence to regulatory guidelines are essential for maintaining the integrity of pharmaceutical products and protecting public health. Ultimately, a robust risk management framework and toxicology practices are fundamental pillars of the pharmaceutical industry, promoting confidence in the safety and efficacy of medications.

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